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Cardiac Cousins?

The Surprising Connection between Takotsubo and Oshtoran Syndrome

Takotsubo cardiomyopathy (Broken-Heart Syndrome) and H63D Syndrome Type-3, clinically known as Oshtoran Syndrome, share astonishing and intriguing similarities in their cardiac symptoms pathophysiology, especially regarding catecholamine overstimulation. While Takotsubo is typically an acute, stress-induced cardiomyopathy with reversible dysfunction, Oshtoran Syndrome presents with a chronic progression of catecholaminergic and mitochondrial dysfunction, and, less often other cardiac symptoms. These facts alone make an exploration all the more crucial because with Oshtoran Syndrome and Takotsubo Cardiomyopathy two seemingly distinct conditions partly share common pathogenic mechanisms, particularly involving chronically elevated levels of catecholamines and sudden or cyclic “adrenergic storms”. We hypothesize that both syndromes may be part of a wide spectrum of diseases related to catecholamine overstimulation, with Oshtoran

Syndrome presenting a much more chronic and dangerous form due to the persistent presence of NTBI, which is not the case with Takotsubo cardiomyopathy - or it is an aspect that has been overlooked in Takotsubo patients. Our aim is to draw parallels between these conditions, provide evidence for overlapping mechanisms, and explore potential therapeutic strategies that could benefit both syndromes.^{9-17,30,31,32}

Catecholamines

Takotsubo cardiomyopathy is a not sufficient enough characterized condition in which acute emotional or physical stress leads to transient left ventricular dysfunction. In contrast, Oshtoran Syndrome represents a complex multi-systemic disorder characterized by persistent autonomic dysfunctions affecting every organ, mitochondrial impairments, and chronically elevated catecholaminergic activity, which is highly concerning. Despite their different temporal profiles - Takotsubo being acute and reversible, while Oshtoran Syndrome is chronic - both conditions have one striking common feature: a massive pathological overstimulation of the sympathetic nervous system, particularly through catecholamines, especially adrenaline and noradrenaline. We proposes a unifying hypothesis that these two conditions, although distinct in clinical presentation, share similar underlying mechanisms, particularly in the context of autonomic dysregulation and catecholamine-induced myocardial injury. Additionally, we remember the medical community that NTBI-iron and autonomic dysfunctions play a critical role in maintaining the chronicity of cardiac dysfunction in Oshtoran Syndrome. These factors are not yet known to be of importance in Takotsubo cardiomyopathy, either because they are absent or have been overlooked to date.^{1,8,9-28}

Materials and Methods

This study relies on a comparative analysis of existing academic literature, focusing on the pathophysiology of both syndromes. Data were extracted from peer-reviewed journals, case studies, and clinical reports related to Takotsubo cardiomyopathy and Oshtoran Syndrome, particularly focusing on:

- Catecholamine toxicity and its effects on myocardial cells.
- Role of NTBI in mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress.
- Chronic sympathetic overstimulation in O-Syndrome versus acute adrenergic surges in BHS.
- Clinical parallels in arrhythmogenic presentations and left ventricular involvement.

Results

1. **Catecholamine Overstimulation:** Both syndromes exhibit elevated massive catecholamine levels. In Takotsubo, this is a transient response to acute stress, leading to myocardial stunning and ventricular dysfunction. In Oshtoran Syndrome, high baseline catecholamine levels and (nor-)adrenaline storms are chronic and recurrent, contributing to a rather broad variety of progressive cardiac damage and arrhythmias, including conduction issues like left bundle branch blocks (LBBB). The persistent nature of catecholaminergic activity in Oshtoran Syndrome, mediated by a dysregulated autonomic nervous system, exacerbates the chronicity of cardiac symptoms.
2. **Role of NTBI and Oxidative Stress:** In Oshtoran Syndrome, NTBI contributes to chronic oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction, leading to long-term cardiac damage. While this mechanism might be absent in Takotsubo (aka 'Broken Heart Syndrome'), oxidative stress in Takotsubo is theorized, not proven, to result from acute catecholamine-induced free radical

generation. However, the presence of non-transferrin bound iron (NTBI) in Takotsubo has not been explored to date, possibly due to its extreme difficulty in detection. NTBI is not visible in MRI, CT scans, X-rays, or histopathology, even in cases of massive overload. Consequently, no published papers have addressed the potential role of NTBI in Takotsubo. In contrast, the presence of NTBI has been proven in Oshtoran Syndrome, where it exacerbates the condition's effects by promoting ongoing oxidative damage to cardiomyocytes and other tissues throughout the entire body in union with chronically and pathologically high catecholamine levels.

3. **Catecholamines:** Both syndromes show a propensity for arrhythmias. In Takotsubo cardiomyopathy, arrhythmias are typically transient and resolve as the heart recovers. In Oshtoran Syndrome, however, arrhythmias are recurrent and often progress to conduction defects such as left bundle branch block (LBBB) and other block types. Additionally, Oshtoran Syndrome patients often experience a drop in left ventricular ejection fraction (LV-EF), indicating chronic heart failure. The long-term progression of minor arrhythmias to severe complications in Oshtoran Syndrome, despite beta-blocker therapy, suggests a deeper involvement of autonomic dysregulation, which is not as evident in Takotsubo. And, one should never forget: the primary drivers of autonomic dysregulation in Oshtoran Syndrome are catecholamines.
4. **Therapeutic Interventions:** The use of various benzodiazepines, weak opiates, non-selective beta-blockers (Propranolol), and a-blockers (specifically Doxazosin) in Oshtoran Syndrome to control both the autonomic storms and possible cardiac arrhythmias has shown very robust efficacy. In contrast, Takotsubo is typically managed with supportive care and selective beta-blockers. However, nobody has proven to this day that this is the best way to treat Takotsubo. The success of neurologically focused treatments in Oshtoran Syndrome raises the question of whether similar approaches could be

beneficial in preventing recurrent episodes in patients with chronic forms of Takotsubo.

Discussion

The findings from this comparative analysis suggest that pathological and severe catecholamine overstimulation is a shared mechanism in both syndromes, though the chronic nature of Oshtoran Syndrome distinguishes it. The involvement of NTBI in Oshtoran Syndrome adds an additional layer of complexity, perpetuating mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress, which may explain the chronic progression of cardiac symptoms. In contrast, the acute nature of Takotsubo typically allows for spontaneous recovery once the catecholamine surge subsides. However, this is not universal, and notably, there is a lack of research exploring the potential role of NTBI in Takotsubo cardiomyopathy.

These observations underscore the need to re-examine Takotsubo cardiomyopathy, especially in cases where a chronic form is suspected. The potential use of non-cardiological medication, such as quite high dose benzodiazepines, propranolol, and doxazosin, could be explored further in chronic Takotsubo, mirroring the approach routinely employed in Oshtoran management.

Further research is needed to explore the molecular pathways linking catecholamine activity, autonomic dysfunctions and NTBI in both syndromes. Investigating whether Takotsubo patients have underlying mitochondrial dysfunction or abnormal iron metabolism may offer new insights into why some cases resolve spontaneously while others develop chronic symptoms.

Conclusion

The hypothesis that Takotsubo (Broken-Heart) Syndrome and Oshtoran Syndrome share overlapping pathomechanisms driven by catecholamines opens new avenues for research and treatment. While Takotsubo is typically self-limiting, the chronicity of Oshtoran Syndrome, potentially due to NTBI

and persistent elevated catecholaminergic levels, requires a different therapeutic approach. By leveraging insights from the treatment of Oshtoran Syndrome, it may be possible to improve outcomes for patients with chronic or recurrent forms of Takotsubo. Future research should aim to elucidate the role of NTBI in cardiac dysfunction and explore novel interventions targeting both autonomic regulation and oxidative stress.

Conflicts of Interest

None declared.

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